

Effectiveness of Social Media for Learning

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ABSTRACT

Social Media networks have broad acceptance in current status. Almost everyone who has access with internet is linked with some kind of social communication using available social medias. Now social Medias are providing lots of utility to its users. This paper studies utility of its are useful for all learners . So the paper explain usefulness of any type of media in any field of education. Youth gain lot's of knowledge through technology in society .That why it is important for young learners Social media can be used effectively to build brand awareness, as well as by people to share brand positives and negatives. The point is that no matter how you slice it social media isn't a passing fad. It is becoming a standard communication platform that has dramatically changed the way that brands and consumers interact with one another.

KEYWORDS: learning, students, social media

INTRODUCTION

Matter of social media is the social reciprocal action among members in which they create, share or transfer information and ideas in basic networks and communities. Michael Haenlein explain social media as a group of internet-based applications that build on the ideological and technological foundations of Web 2.0 and that allow the creation and exchange of user-generated content. Moreover, social media depend on mobile and web-based technologies to construct highly interactive platforms through which individuals and communities share, co-create, discuss, and modify user originate content. They introduce meaningful and omnipresent changes to communication between organizations, communities, and individuals. Social Media Networks are developing and it's been reaching to large people day by day. Today other kind of social media exist. That's why it is famous now because the possibility of the internet , technologies which useful for us this availability to our hands like Mobiles, Tablets etc. It has so many efficacies in peoples. This can be good or bad. This paper makes the importance of technology and social media in Education. This topic Utility of because 90 percentage of the people with 19-30 age limit are in part of technology. For this help of achivment of educational aims. To make the there must be communication between students and teachers through the network of Social media. Email can be a best way of communication between students and teachers.

Information source of Social Media

It's changes type of study in present learners. Students are now indicating technology to get the information through social media. Real knowledge regarding which we want to know is possible on the internet and best medium to get the

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knowledge. Almost faculty agrees that reciprocal nature of online and mobile technologies create better learning background. The Social Media can act as a medium for communication for students and teachers using the communication service. The Social Media are very effective in research objectives social networking sites, like much else on the Internet, represent a moving target for researchers and policy makers.

- The Social Media can be important in all kinds of educations. The Content communities and Blogs can be act as a Digital Library.
- It can provide useful contents which are not usable by nearest resources. Content Communities can provide text , visible information.
- You Tube like Content Community members are giving lots of education programs to learners.
- YouTube also improved student's digital skills and opportunity for peer learning and problem solving.
- Online communities are also helping the learners in their education. They provide instant communications.
- Educators research supports earlier findings that suggest that active involvement in online communities of practice can produce significant value for educators, students, schools, and districts.
- One of the strategy to make the information usable is by sharing through social medias. The person's in the online communities benefits other persons with their knowledge.

Social media for students

Social Medias are very helpful in finding better career for students. The Colleges, institutions are fully active in Social

Media with their online status like College profile in Facebook. Students can refer the college's and institution's profile and choose the satisfactory colleges and institutions for their higher studies.

AA survey last year found that 71% of students used media to research schools, 40% said they used it as a research tool when where to enrol. This has prompted college and universities to use social media as an informative recruitment tool, with 96% of schools using social media in their online recruitment efforts.

Social Media for professionals

- Social Media is also very useful for those who seek for jobs and those in search for careers.
- Social media is LinkedIn for professionals. The people use this Social Media as an useful tool for job hunting.
- There are many more Professional Networking Sites apart from LinkedIn but it may be the biggest one in across countries .
- The LinkedIn Network is totally intended for professionals. It helps to make professional connected network to build a better career.
- It also allows showcasing the user's professional gallery which consist of the work examples and videos and slide share etc.

Educational approaches and benefits of social media

➤ Good Communication

A student can connect with anyone use of social media such as smart phone, tablet, computer and internet. learner can exchange questions , phone calls, video calls with anyone. They don't need to wait and meet the teacher physically. Social media promote learning by offering support with sharing documents.

➤ Important Information Online

Social media networks and up websites are providing plenty of information that can be useful to students. The educational benefits of social networking sites are help students prepare for important lessons, concepts . Social media websites will contain the latest data on various school subjects and thus, the students have the opportunity to survey and look into what is new.

➤ Helpful for Parents

Social media help the parents stay involved in the child's education . The school's give feed to parents can be updated on school-related activities, projects, and events that are happening. These are all positive impacts media have on parents' communication with the school so as to learn about, share and observe their children's' academic and personal progress at school.

➤ Developed Literacy, Communication, Reading Skills

It is usually examined that students are bored of reading and writing, the internet and social media provide plenty of online information which often students are more inclined to read. Online messages, comments, news, articles, and books provide an endless list of information to be read, and students are motivated to devote their time and put some extra efforts towards their learning.

➤ Opportunities for Distance Learning

Other great advantage of social media in education is distance learning opportunities. There are many disadvantaged students who are not able to acquire formal education by attending regular classes in an educational institution. With the help of various online social media tools along with social media, modern educators are able to engage students through distance learning programs.

Disadvantages of social media

lack of privacy being discussed now, there are a lot many negative aspects to social media.

- Very recently one of the leading social media's was accused of compromising its user's privacy and contact details for profit making. It leads to a scary scenario to live in this cyber space.
- Negative aspects the generations before the social media had a very fulfilling and harmonious social life where they had very good connections between their fellow beings and with nature, which has been lacking ever since the advancement of social media.
- Present time generation today indulge their time and resource more into the hollow and many a times fake relationships endorsed by these profit oriented social giants.
- Recently many developing and developed countries, with diverse cultural background, witnessed an insidious chain of incidents, namely the suicide of many an account users, mainly young girls, women and also a lot of young men too.
- The reason being, a lot of ill minded people playing tricks at cheating those less enlightened kids of the social media block. Many girls committed suicide for their photos being morphed and used for the promotion of many adult products and also fake accounts intended for character assassination.
- In short social media is projecting a false picture of the real world that we live in, thereby creating and moulding an ill-informed generation of unrealistic, unenlightened individuals whom we call "Homosapiens".

Conclusion

The Social Media is now with lots of services and sources. These services and resources can make use by the users of Social Media. This paper is used to study its importance in education filed and found out that it is very helpful tool in education purposes and beyond. Students can make use of the interaction services, blogging services, group services in their studies and also use Social Media or search for colleges and career and other job opportunities.

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